

MAIN AREAS OF DEVELOPMENT OF A DIGITAL ECONOMY

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Abstract. *Digital economy, that is, activities based on digital technologies, today provide an opportunity to develop all areas of society. Just one example, in recent years, new forms of innovation can be counted - e-services, online sales, distance education, in other words, these practices that we can do without leaving home through telephone, computer or other information technologies have become normal for us. turned around.*

Keywords: *Digital economy, digital governance, economy, market economy, digital technology, digitalization.*

ОСНОВНЫЕ НАПРАВЛЕНИЯ РАЗВИТИЯ ЦИФРОВОЙ ЭКОНОМИКИ

Аннотация. *Цифровая экономика, то есть деятельность, основанная на цифровых технологиях, сегодня дает возможность развивать все сферы жизни общества. Только один пример, за последние годы можно насчитать новые формы инноваций - электронные услуги, онлайн-продажи, дистанционное обучение, другими словами, эти практики, которыми мы можем заниматься, не выходя из дома, посредством телефона, компьютера или других информационных технологий, стали нормой. для нас. развернулся.*

Ключевые слова: *цифровая экономика, цифровое управление, экономика, рыночная экономика, цифровые технологии, цифровизация.*

The development of a digital economy has only a few advantages for the country and mankind. For example, the development of information and communication sectors will allow us to save a lot of time, make the most of it efficiently and wisely, the most valuable of human resources. If we buy an electronic format instead of a paper-published copy of a book, we will have made the most of our precious time. Through the development of information technology, we have saved not only our time and even our finances. To make utility payments, we are not required to spend hours in queues or go to banks, we can make reliable payments at any time anywhere. This process will also be very useful for our women with disabilities or young goose. In addition to performing their home punches, they will be able to easily purchase the products they need or rollers from online stores. In addition, digital technology can also be used effectively in education, informing the student of the level of learning, the grades he or she receives from the subjects, the continuity and achievements of the teacher and the student in the classroom.

World experience shows that while the development of the digital economy enjoys unlimited benefits, it creates many problems as an objective process. When it comes to the digital economy, economic activity is usually associated with the production, sale and consumption of goods and services using digital technology, as well as the use of e-commerce, the Internet, and the Internet. After the incredible success of some start-ups in the digital economy, getting rid of the dot-com crisis (this business model is a term used for companies based on full Internet activities) and especially after the capitalization of Internet giants, equalized (the company's profit increases its share capital), then exceeded the capitalization of

large enterprises in traditional sectors of the economy, the importance of the digital economy began to grow.

The formation and development of the digital economy creates a number of problems. First, creating more efficient technologies for information usage and processing and application significantly reduces transaction costs (costs associated with searching and processing found data) and improves the flexibility and efficiency of the economy. However, this does not happen if the old technologies of information processing are not lost at the same time and the share of transaction costs increases due to increased costs of information protection, assessing its reliability. Online business activism drastically reduces, and sometimes eliminates, the need for intermediaries and agents.

Digital economy is one of the most relevant topics today. Basically, how to develop this topic in Uzbekistan is in the hands of our young people. The term "digital economy" was first coined by Don Tapscott in 1995. "Digital Economy: Promise and Peril in the Age of Networked Intelligence" as a special concept. This publication highlights fundamental innovations (semiconductors, processors), basic technologies (computers), and connecting infrastructure (internet and telecommunications networks) to the main components of the digital economy.

In developed countries, the introduction of a digital economy has already been introduced. (Matthew 24:14; 28:19, 20) In the context of the globalization of the world economy and the development of technology, the economic development of Uzbekistan cannot be achieved without the development of a digital economy.

Digital technology development is critical to achieving almost all economic and social goals and covers all countries, industries and stakeholders. Today, there is a big difference between countries that do not have internet access in the world and countries with much higher digitization rates, such as in less developed countries, whereas in less developed countries, every fifth person uses the internet, four out of every five have access to the Internet. This is just one example of digital division. In other areas such as digital data and capabilities for advanced technology, the gap is considerable.

For example, Africa and Latin America host less than 5% of all rental data centers in the world. If necessary measures are not taken, this gap will lead to a further increase in inequality in the distribution of income. Therefore, it is important to understand how this evolution will affect developing countries in terms of creating value and benefits, and what needs to be done to improve the current situation. Digital platforms are playing an increasingly important role in the global economy. The total value of platform companies with market capitalization of more than \$100 million in 2017 exceeded an estimated \$7 trillion, up 67% from 2015. Some global digital platforms have gained very strong market positions in certain segments. For example, about 90% of internet search engines are occupied by Google. Facebook holds two-thirds of the global social media market and is the most popular social media platform in more than 90% of countries.

International experience shows that digital technology today is rapidly developing mainly in the scientific community and in the private sector. Therefore, the state should create a favorable ecosystem, supporting innovative projects in these areas. Although there are payment systems that allow Click, Payme, M-bank, Upay, Easy and other online payments, the rate of online payments for mobile payments, the Internet, and communal payments is not high. In

2017, 34 percent of account holders made a digital payment. Compared to 96 per cent in the UK. We need to develop this area and develop e-commerce and electronic transfers. If the digital payment is 34% in Uzbekistan, we need to increase this figure to 100%.

First of all, the digital economy is the main cousin of corruption and the "black economy." Because numbers seal everything, store it in memory, quickly provide information when necessary. Under such circumstances, it is impossible to hide any information, make secret transactions, not provide full information about it or this activity, the computer will display it all. The abundance and systematicity of the data does not allow false and malicious activities, because it is impossible to deceive the system. As a result, it will not be possible to wash away "dirty money," steal funds, spend ineffectively and aimlessly, increase or hide them. This will increase the flow of legal funds to the economy, taxes will be paid on time and correctly, budget distribution will be open, social sector-oriented funds will not be stolen, money allocated to schools, hospitals, roads will fully reach, etc.

Also, the fact that the state has chosen a way to develop the digital economy opens up new directions in the field of information technology and in the field of electronic document circulation in general. The turn towards "digital technologies" was caused by the development of the worldwide Internet and quality communication. It is worth noting that today users of this system are actively using Telegram bots to order food, various perfumes and modern clothing products. Various internet stores and electronic payment systems are also actively developing. So our citizens are confident in making electronic transactions. It is only up to the present that users are doing small deals that do not require significant costs, while not very willing to increase the average purchase volume. The current issue is the development of medium- and large-scale economic transactions and the implementation of financial transactions through digital technology.

In conclusion, by developing a digital economy, we will have greatly facilitated human lifestyles, and its growth will not affect the governance of the government because by digitization we will have prevented many corruption and crimes, and of course the country's development will be significantly improved.

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